

UNIVERSITY OF TARTU
Institute of Computer
Science

Report on Empirical Study of Information Security and Privacy Management in Intelligent Transportation Systems in Estonia and South Moravia

Mariia Bakhtina¹, Raimundas Matulevicius¹, and Lukas Malina²

¹Institute of Computer Science, University of Tartu, Narva mnt. 18, Tartu, 51009, Estonia

²Department of Telecommunications, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Communication, Brno University of Technology, Technicka 12, Brno, 61600, Czech Republic

bakhtina@ut.ee, rma@ut.ee, malina@vut.cz

Cite this report as:

Bakhtina, M., Matulevicius, R., & Malina, L. (2024). *Report on Empirical Study of Information Security and Privacy Management in Intelligent Transportation Systems in Estonia and South Moravia*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10960046>

1 Introduction

This report provides results of the study that aim to identify the challenges of ensuring the security and privacy of information in the evolving ITSs characterised by the gap between state-of-the-art research proposals and real-life usage of them. The main research question (MRQ) of the study is the following: ***What are the challenges in information security and privacy management in ITSs?*** To answer MRQ, we divide it into the following sub-questions:

- RQ₁. What is the level of ITSs maturity?
- RQ₂. In which areas do operate organisations which use or maintain ITSs?
- RQ₃. What kind of information is being protected in ITSs?
- RQ₄. Which information security and privacy management standards support ITSs?
- RQ₅. Which information security and privacy management methodologies do the organisations which use or maintain ITSs follow?
- RQ₆. Which information security and privacy management technologies do the organisations which use or maintain ITSs use?

In this study, we consider that an intelligent transportation system (ITS) is a (set of) system(s) that enables ride-hailing, smart parking, electronic toll collection, and the creation of connected vehicles. First, we a framework for information security and privacy management (i.e., FISP-ProCOP) is presented (Sec. 3). Then, we use FISP-ProCOP as a theoretical model for two empirical studies. The first study is a literature review that results in the defined state-of-the-art aspects and measures that help to assure information security and privacy in ITSs (Sec. 4 - 5). The second study is a survey-based analysis of the running ITSs within the selected region that results in the comparison of the real-life ITSs and the used measures for InfoSec & PM with the state-of-the-art measures defined through the literature review (Sec. 6 - 7). As the researched area for the study, we select two regions in the European Union (EU) – South Moravia in the Czech Republic and Estonia – where ITSs are used and which have market actors specialised in cybersecurity. As a result, the comparison allows us to identify both the challenges of addressing InfoSec & PM perceived by the organisations themselves and the identified through the research gaps of using state-of-the-art security privacy measures. The report contains a detailed results description of the study in [1].

2 Background of the researched regions

As the population of our study, we select the organisations contributing to intelligent transportation systems in two selected regions - Estonia and the South Moravian region in the Czech Republic. The two targeted regions are of similar size in terms of population, economy and the level of digital development, as depicted in Table 1. South Moravia (hereinafter referred to as “SM”) stands as a hub for the ICT industry and education in the Czech Republic, boasting a smart specialisation strategy of cybersecurity. SM region has the largest concentration of software development companies, SMEs and start-ups that are producing and developing advanced ICT solutions and technologies in the Czech Republic. Estonia ranks among the world’s most advanced digital societies. While Estonia is a target of a range of cyber threats, it is ranked second by the National Cyber Security Index (as of the end of 2023) ³. According to ICT Development Index (IDI) of 2021 ⁴ and digital economy and society index report of 2022 ⁵, the selected regions have similar scores of the digital development in general, and in terms of the level of advancement in digital skills, the number of ITC specialists and digital technology integration which are the enablers of the ITS development and usage.

Table 1: Comparison of targeted regions’ characteristics [2]

Region	GDP ¹ , mln EUR	Population ¹ , mln	IDI ¹ , score	DESI assessment ²			
				DESI, score	At least basic digital skills, % of population	ICT specialists, % of population	Integration of dig. technologies, score
South Moravia	28.1	1.2	86.1*	49.1*	60*	4.6*	33.8*
Estonia	36	1.3	96.9	56.5	56	6.2	36.5

* - the score was calculated to Czech Republic overall, not for SM region specifically,

¹ - based on the data of 2021, ² - based on the data of 2022

³ <https://ncsi.ega.ee/country/ee/>

⁴ https://www.itu.int/hub/publication/d-ind-ict_mdd-2023-2/

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/desi>

3 Framework for Information Security & Privacy Management (FISP-ProCOP)

Based on the reviewed information security frameworks and models, and considering the need for a model which would help analyse the state of information security and privacy management on the intelligent systems, we developed a new framework InfoSec & PM (see Figure 2). The framework is based on BMIS [3], McCube [4] and RMIAS [5] models. Assuring the privacy of users' data is directly connected with securing it (e.g., based on GDPR), thus, in our study, we consider information security management and privacy management as tightly coupled tasks. Consequently, the proposed framework does not differentiate attributes of the context that affect only one of them (privacy or security) and do not affect another. The proposed framework is more granular than the reviewed ones and, thus, is more applicable for the purpose of our study – defining the static state of information security and privacy management in the context of intelligent socio-technical systems (e.g., intelligent transportation systems).

Dimension	Category	Attribute
P. People	PA. Actors	Actors, stakeholders, entities Goals, tasks, motives
	PR. Relationships	Relationships and dependencies between actors
O. Organisation	OS. Strategy	Purpose for the system usage, org. design & strategy Challenges to address
	OC. Formal Constraints	Legislation, regulation, standard
	OI. Information Involved	Type of information used
		How the information is manipulated
Security criteria Privacy objectives		
C. Sec. & Privacy Countermeasures	CP. Policies & Practices	Policies & practices
	CE. Training & Education	Training & education
	CT. Technology	Architectural measures
		Use case-oriented technological measures
		Cryptographic building blocks Others technological measures
Pr. Processes	PrL. System Lifecycle	Security as a part of the system lifecycle
	PrU. Usage of the System	Use cases of the system as a part of the business processes

Figure 2: A framework for information security and privacy management in the connected systems [1]

The FISP describes four key aspects, i.e. *dimensions*, that, from the business point of view, affect the management of information security and privacy assurance – *Processes, security & privacy Countermeasures, Organisation, and People* (ProCOP). Each dimension contains multiple categories, which are divided by the attributes. Finally, each attribute may have one or more instances of such attribute which correspond to the instantiation of the model to the selected context of the system usage.

While FISP-ProCOP is presented in the form of a matrix, it does not depict relationships between dimensions, categories and attributes, for example, in contrast to RMIAS. On the other hand, due to the tabular structure, our hypothesis is that the model is a more useful tool for depicting the static view of information security and privacy management in the complex information system than other reviewed frameworks and models. Additionally, the assumption is that such a representation of dimensions which affect information security and privacy in the system can help depict the effect of attributes on one another by considering measures usage from multiple perspectives. As a result, FISP-ProCOP should help to cross-validate the assumption of the direct effect of some security and privacy countermeasures on meeting the stated organisational goals (e.g., stated by the standard).

4 Literature Review: Research Method

The goal is to identify the challenges of information security and privacy management in intelligent transportation systems (ITSs). Thus, we (1) define the state-of-the-art measures of Info Sec and privacy management within four dimensions — processes, organisational design, people and technological solutions; (2) survey the companies to compare their measure of Info Sec and privacy management with the state-of-the-art solutions.

First, the state-of-the-art measures were defined based on the literature review (LR) following the guidelines in [6].

Data sources. The search of literature was performed in to the commonly used in the information security databases: Scopus, ACM Digital Library, and Web of Science. These databases were selected because they contain peer-reviewed papers and allows to use complex search queries with logical expressions. Another popular database, namely IEEE Xplore, was not used for the literature search as Scopus already contains papers published in IEEE and, therefore, there is no need to use both these databases together.

Search Strategy. For the literature review, we use the following query: (“security” OR “privacy protection” OR “data protection”) AND (“technologies” OR “measure”)) AND (Industry_name), where instead of Industry_name, we use “vehicle sharing”, “ride-hailing”, “smart parking”, “toll”, and “connected vehicles”, “mobility” and their synonyms. From the selected papers, we extract policies, approaches, methods and techniques for information security and privacy management (referred to later as “measures”).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria. To filter out the papers which were selected using the search string but that are not relevant for our research scope, we defined a few inclusion and exclusion criteria (see Table 2).

Table 2: Inclusion/exclusion criteria [1]

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
IC1. the paper discusses information security of an ITS	EC1. non-English papers
IC2. the paper discusses at least one method or technique of managing information security or privacy in the ITSs	EC2. papers published earlier than 2015
IC3. the paper discusses information security issues to be addressed in the field	EC3. no full access available
IC4. the paper contains an instance of some attributes from the reference model in Fig. 2	EC4. the paper is a duplicate or an earlier version of another paper

Data extraction. After applying the defined exclusion and inclusion criteria to the queried paper, 23 papers have been selected for the data extraction. The data from the review is organised in four dimensions (processes, organisational design, people and technological solutions) based on FISP-ProCOP. The goal of our study is to assess the level of information security and privacy management level of maturity of companies in the intelligent transportation field in accordance with the state-of-the-art measures in the research literature. To achieve the goal, we follow the methodology of experimentation [7].

We prepare an instrument for the experiments. The developed instrument is an assessment model which aims to assess the level of maturity of the security and privacy measures in four dimensions: (1) people, (2) process, (3) organisational design and strategy, and (4) technologies. The instrument is in the form of a survey that should be filled in by the selected participants’ representatives.

5 Literature Review: Results

In this section, we provide an overview of the state-of-the-art aspects of managing security and privacy in intelligent transportation systems. The results are grouped by the sub-types of ITSs and describe what is the goal of the ITSs, key components, stakeholders and processes, challenges of ITSs development in information protection, relevant regulations and standards that guide the ITSs development and support, as well as the security and privacy countermeasure recommended for ITSs.

Our study shows that the research intensity varies from one operation area of intelligent transportation to another, and, for example, smart parking is the most thorough research compared to others. Thus, the results presented in the following subsection may not be complete with respect to the used reference model. When presenting the review results, the missed dimensions or attributes for the operation area mean that we did not find the respective data in the selected literature. Also, we do not include the architectural or technical measures that primarily deliver the main system functionality and do not significantly affect information security or privacy in the ITSs.

The results of the literature review are depicted with respect to the proposed reference model in Appendix I. The tables in the appendix depict the state-of-the-art measures of information security and privacy management in intelligent transportation systems. However, the state-of-the-art measures are missing some of the categories and attributes for the dimensions of People and Organisations. The reason is that we were not able to systematically extract them based on the LR, and the level of details for the missed attributes differs across papers and operation areas of ITSs. The dimensions of Processes from the reference model are not put into the tables, as the LR provided only a general overview of use cases for ITSs and in which business processes it could be used, but the level of process descriptions significantly differ across papers and operation areas.

5.1 Smart Parking (SP)

Smart parking (i.e. SP) is an intelligent transportation system that facilitates searching for a vacant parking slot. Among the literature, smart parking is related to the terms “parking platform”, “smart city”, “parking space sharing”, and “car parking”.

According to the survey in [8], commonly addressed features of the smart parking systems include vacant slot detection, route planning, easy check-in, secure parking, parking status check, cost optimisation and reservation. And in order to achieve these functionalities, smart parking systems may use the following techniques [8]: (i) digitally enhanced parking, (ii) intelligent smart parking, (iii) cloud-based smart parking, (iv) sensor-based smart parking; (v) smart routing; (vi) high-density parking; (vii) vacant slot detection (visual- or sensor-based). Except for the mostly studied SP, there is a more advanced ITS, which is called “*automated valet parking (AVP)*”. AVP facilitates an autonomous vehicle (AV) with scheduling, parking navigation and dropping a user at a predefined drop-off spot, and allows reservation in real time [8].

People Here we enumerate the key stakeholders involved in the development and operation of the smart parking system and give a short description of their role.

Driver (or “parking space requester”) cruises around the city in order to find a parking slot to park a car. The driver is generally willing to pay a fee for using the slot; however, occasionally, they may have the wish to avoid paying or pay as little as possible [9], [10]. The driver is characterised by *concerns* for privacy and security of their personal data [11], [12], which is collected and shared for the parking. A driver may be a citizen or a visitor [13].

Parking supplier (also referred to as parking service (or space) provider) manages and/or owns the parking spots available for occupation by drivers. Supplier is willing to charge drivers with the fee for the parking spots usage [11], [12]. Supplier is also concerned about confidentiality and integrity of the parking slot data [11]. **Parking officer** (or “parking agent”) checks the parking

status of a car to enforce following the parking rules [9], [10], [14] (e.g., payment for the parking). *Internal employee of PSP* with privileged access [9] may have motives to become an insider and access the data managed by the service provider. *Researcher* (external actor) who designs algorithm for smart parking.

Server [9], [10] is the system which connects drivers who search for the parking spot with parking suppliers. Servers are managed by an organisation (i.e. *parking service provider (PSP)*) which is responsible for enabling driver-supplier relationships and for the operation of the Server.

Trusted Authority (TA) (or “trusted third party”) is an entity responsible includes one or more of the mentioned activities [11,15]: (i) initialising the parking system; (ii) registration of drivers and suppliers; (iii) generating public parameters and keys distribution; (iii) manages and issues user credentials. TA’s role may play smart city government [15]. **Timestamp authority (TSA)** issues timestamps upon request [14,9,10]. The designs tend to be too abstract and hard to implemented [16].

Organisation design Purpose and Context. Smart parking aims to address a number of tasks [15,17,13]: (i) optimisation of parking spaces usage due to the limited space available and constant increase of vehicle numbers; (ii) decreasing the city traffic congestion is partially (around 40%) caused by drivers searching for parking spots; (iii) resolving problem of air pollution and wasting driver’s time; (iv) improve performance of city services through smart cities [18,13] and smart usage of transportation infrastructure. The main contextual factors which guide implementation of smart parking are characteristics of the city (e.g., number of the citizens, companies that manage and maintaining parking spots) [13].

Regulations. Among the existing legislation affecting smart parking are: GDPR [9]; local zoning code parking regulations [16], and European Union directive 2010/40/EU (7 July 2010) which defines what is considered as an “intelligent transportation system” [10]. Additionally, [19] mentioned that smart parking is affected by the consumer protection directives (directives 2019/770 and 2019/771) and vehicular safety regulations (including UNECE regulation No 155 (from 2020) and Regulation (EU) 2019/2144 of the European Parliament and of the Council).

Challenges. The literature mentioned quit a number of challenges that guides and restricts the development of SP systems. A set of challenges are related with the *expected system quality*: (i) privacy & security impact on the system users is of a high importance, therefore SP systems should enable secure communication and data privacy [8,18] in order to prevent identity and trajectory leakage [15]; (ii) quick and efficient matching of driver’s parking requests with suppliers slots [11] due to sensitivity to network delay for real-time service [13]; (iii) high flexibility expectation from such system quality characteristics as platform independence, OS independence, exchangeability, cross-layer algorithms, scalability and efficiency [16]; and (iv) balance between privacy and efficiency of the parking system [18]. The second group of challenges concerns the system *functionality and its impact* on the environment: (v) congestion avoidance is one of the challenging task for SP [8]; (vi) scheduling contributes to the increased user experience and decreased energy consumption and costs [8]; (vii) green parking is an important part towards environmental protection through booking online, applying green energy, efficient scheduling and path guidance [8]; (viii) preventing unauthorised occupation of the allocated parking spot [13]. The next third group describes the challenges of SP *implementation*: (ix) data minimisation as one of the most important parts of the privacy by design strategy [18]; (x) heterogeneous networks [16]; (xi) providing system security before the system is launched [18]; (xii) resource-constrained devices usage [16]. Finally, the last group of challenges originates from the *context* where SP systems are developed: (xiii) interoperability issues due to existence of different proprietary solutions for parking from different parking suppliers across the city [13]; (xiv) absence of IoT industry regulations [18] and standards [16]; (xv) absence of national strategy for development smart

environments or cities with an action plan that clearly defines the goals and how to achieve them [13], good practices to follow during the smart city solutions development.

Information. There are two categories of information manipulated during the parking process: collected or manipulated in the pure form, and information that can be extracted from the aggregated data. So, let us describe what are the examples of such information and consider its characteristics which guides the parking systems.

The information collected or manipulated in the pure form and the security criteria may include driver- and parking slot-related data: (i) privacy of *driver's GPS location* [12,11,13]; (ii) anonymity of the *driver's identity* [12] incl. by means of assuring anonymous payments [11]; (iii) confidentiality of *driver's parking history* (i.e. unlinkability) [12,11]; (iv) integrity of the *parking slots payments status* [12] to enable public verifiability (e.g. by the parking officer), which can be neglected by the driver's motive for payment avoidance (e.g., harvesting attack); (v) integrity [12,11] as well as authenticity, accuracy and completeness [13] of *parking transactions*; (vi) availability of *parking slot status* [13] to allow driver to find available slots.

The information which can be extracted from the aggregated data includes (i) *mobility patterns* of citizens living in the city (aggregated) [12], (ii) workplace, home address, and location commonly visited socialising places [12,11], (iii) citizens profiles [15].

Process An example of the parking process solution [12,15] includes ten steps: (1) *initialisation of the system* incl. area partition, parametrisation of crypto systems, solicitation, users registration in the trusted authority; (2) *registration* incl. acquiring credentials to the service provider's system and coins (if required by the architecture), and parking offers generation; (3) *parking service initiation* incl. logging in to service provider, (4) *initiating parking request*; (5) obtaining info about available parking slot; (6) *parking reservation*; (7) *payment*; (8) *verification* of the parking by a parking officer; (9) *parking cancellation* (optional); (10) *reputation rating* (optional).

According to the survey in [8], there are a few key processes related to smart parking systems: (i) information collection; (ii) system development; (iii) parking service dissemination; (iv) smart parking system management facilities with respect to the traditional parking solutions.

We also have identified process design patterns for the parking process which could support system security and privacy. First, a payment status (in a form of ticket) of a car should not be available for check unless a parking officer is located close to the parked car [9,10]. While the only information obtained the parking status of is a boolean value (Yes/No) [10]. Additionally, during the ticket inspection, issued tickets signed by a service provider are checked together with those signed by the on-board unit data [9].

For the payment, it is proposed to allow payment using a smartphone [10,14,9], so that payment is done for short-duration time slots using pre-paid e-coins [14,9] within the SP system's mobile app. In such a setting, driver's app should receives e-coins and parking tickets which are signed by the server and the e-coins can be proven to be authentic. Upon receiving, they are immediately verified by an app on the correctness [9]. Parking tickets can be revoked by a driver in advance without revealing the vehicle it was. Additionally, it is recommended that driver's identifiers and not included in location (ticket) proofs [10].

Security & Privacy Countermeasures Before proceeding to countermeasures, we need to mention the technological settings (key system components) for the smart parking systems. First, there is a *vehicle* managed by a driver; a vehicle may be equipped with an onboarding device (e.g., RFID device) [9,10]. Second, there is a *parking lot terminal* that manages access to the off-street parking spaces [15]. Additionally, there are commonly used IoT devices for tracking parking occupancy [13]. Vehicles may be connected to vehicular ad hoc networks (VANET) [10].

Following the framework in Fig. 2, we present the identified from the literature technological countermeasures starting from architectural, following with the use case oriented and cryptographic building blocks.

Architectural countermeasures. In the context of building an SP system from the existing separate components, [13] proposed to aim for horizontal platform for loosely-coupled integration of vertical solutions.

Some solution are focused on ensuring confidentiality of the manipulated assets. For example, storage of sensitive data (e.g., parking tickets, location) locally in device where the parking app is used by a drivers [9,16] can help to fulfill driver's privacy requirements, usage of *secret sharing* [18] helps to improve reliability and confidentiality of the system in general, while *secure multiparty computation* [18] helps to protect driver's and supplier's confidentiality.

The state-of-the-art research also proposed a number of blockchain-based architectural solutions [15,17,18,12,20]. For example, Secure blockchain-based privacy-preserving valet parking protocol (B-park) [20] is based on the *Pointcheval-Sander (PS) group signature* scheme and is proved to be meet the following security requirements of anonymity, conversion blindness, nonframeability, and traceability. Meanwhile, Blockchain-enabled PriParkRec [12] utilises Zero-Knowledge proof (ZKP), homomorphic encryption, oblivious pseudorandom function (OPRF), privacy-preserving payment, blind certificate authorities to enable privacy-preserving electronic toll collection. Another privacy-preserving parking system architecture [15] is secured with revocable anonymous credentials and blinded signatures. The solution also relies on blockchain and smart contracts technologies for storing parking transaction to prevent single point of failure. Finally, in [17] authors advocates for a decentralised privacy-preserving system based on the consortium blockchain.

To secure data in transit, the literature proposes to use some of the following solutions based on the desired security criteria: black networks (BN) [18] to insure integrity, confidentiality and privacy; trusted software-defined networking (SDN) controller [18] to insure availability and secure routing; unified registry (UR) [18] to support identity management, mobility authentication, and authorization; key management system (KMS) [18] to insure efficient key distribution for (a)symmetric keys; and, finally, secure transport protocol (e.g., TLS) [9].

As for payment-oriented architectural design, in [14,9,10] authors proposes a pay-by-phone parking system – a privacy-preserving payment system to conduct payment for short-duration time slots using pre-paid e-coins.

Technical countermeasures per functionality. The state-of-the-art privacy-preserving *navigation systems* are VSPN [11], PRIN [11], and CPARN [11]. While *slot search* could be protected by employing private information retrieval [17] (for private retrieval of parking offers by a driver), hashmap storing of all parking locations with pertinent information in order to enable accurate and quick data retrieval [11].

For *membership revocation*, participatory sensing architecture SPPEAR [11] and provably secure group signature scheme CRBE [11] are recommended. For *payment*, researchers proposed to use anonymous payment systemes (e.g., Fair Payment System [11], WhoPay [11], Bitcoin [11], TOR [11]), blockchain (e.g., Ethereum) and smart contracts [15] for storage of parking transactions and preventing single point of failure. Secure *user authentication* can be achieved through attribute-based credentials [15] that allows pseudonymising user access credentials, short randomisable signatures [17] for anonymous authentication, or using biometric-based authentication [18].

For security *parking permit (ticket) generation or parking reservation*, the literature proposed to use blind signature [15] to hide content of parking permits and, thereby, assure confidentiality of the parking time and location, not allowing a parking service provider to know details of the parking. Alternatively, presenting proof-of-knowledge for requesting the parking could be implemented with (i) no attributes (completely anonymous proof of the access token validity); (ii) generalised

attributes; or (iii) VPN attribute [15]. Finally, short randomisable group signatures [11] can allow querying PSP server in a privacy-preserving manner. As for the *ticket payment verification*, blockchain [15] or proof-of-knowledge could be used.

Cryptographic building blocks. As it was briefly mentioned before, the key cryptographic block that enable security- and privacy-preservation in SP systems are the following: Zero-Knowledge proof (ZKP) [12,16], homomorphic encryption [12], oblivious pseudorandom function (OPRF) [12], private set intersection (PSI) [12], anonymous credential system [12], blind signatures [15,9] (including RSA blind signatures [9,10], RSA simulated signature[9], and partially blind signatures[9]), elliptic curve cryptography (ECC)[9,16,10], optimal asymmetric encryption padding[9] and hash-based message authentication codes (HMAC) [10].

Other supporting technological countermeasures mentioned in the literature aims to support the smart parking systems security in general and include intrusion detection system (e.g., based on machine learning and data mining [18]) and additional cybersecurity measures as firewalls, antivirus, high-availability platforms [9].

Policies and practices. The discussed in the literature policies for privacy assurance include privacy by design [18], privacy-related testing and verification as an integral part of the system testing [18], integration of privacy architecture into the system development [18], and avoiding recording unrelated data [18] (which corresponds to following the data minimisation principles). And for supporting security of the parking systems, secure programming as a part of system development [9] and usage of sensor devices which have built-in security measures [16] are considered.

As for training and education as a countermeasures, the reviewed literature has not mentioned any recommended training. The studies are mostly focused on the system design and developments stages and protecting from security and privacy threats based on exploited the system's vulnerabilities by a malicious attacker.

5.2 Ride Sharing (i.e. carpooling)

The purpose of carpooling systems is to enable passengers share the car during the same ride for more efficient usage of vehicles, decreasing the cost of rides and city collision avoidance. Similar to carpooling systems are ride-sharing systems, which are a platform that connects drivers of cars with passengers who need a ride.

The terms which are often used interchangeably are “ride-hailing”, “ride-sharing”, and “car-pooling”. Depending on the driver's motives, ride-sharing looks more like a taxi or like sharing the trip with a few other passengers who need to approach a similar destination [21]. Some work is focused on the future of the vehicle sharing, namely usage of the driver-less autonomous vehicles and assuring data privacy [22] and security in such an advanced settings.

People There are three stakeholders involved in the usage or support of the carpooling. **Passenger** is looking for the car in the nearest area for commuting to their destination. The passenger is interested in using the car together with other passengers who may be people the passenger is not acquainted with. The passenger wants to keep his pick-up and drop-off location confidential and to avoid sharing it with other potential passengers [22]. Passengers may have malicious motives for using the system with the purpose of revealing information about other passengers.

Driver a person who drives the car during the shared ride. A driver can be the owner of the vehicle or not. The driver may have one of the following objectives: (i) looks for passengers who would share the ride with him as they need to make a similar trip with the driver; (ii) looks for passenger who needs a ride to any destination.

Ride-sharing system provider manages the ride-sharing system that matches a passenger requesting a ride with a driver to execute the ride. Often, the provider has access to passenger's identity, location, and time of the trip as this data is stored in the system and can be accessed by

the provider company representatives [22]. The system provider is considered a semi-honest actor as it is not in their interest to harm the reputation of the system.

Organisation design Information. In carpooling, the key asset to be protected is information of *passenger's trip* and *passenger's location*. Neither other passengers, nor system provider should learn (any) information about the passengers' trip in general [22,21]. Service provider neither should know the passengers' initial locations nor the centroid of few passengers' initial locations [22].

Process From the process point of view, there are two main steps where security and privacy are of the most importance as its assurance affects the business process design. First, privacy-preserving *group forming* which is the way of defining a group of passengers who share the vehicle within the same ride. The group forming is based on the preferred pick-up points, drop-off points, and time of travel [22]. Second, carpooling should enable privacy-preserving *fair meeting* (i.e. pick-up) point selection that can be done through (i) relying on the server that manages vehicle-sharing system, (ii) relying on a cloud or a trusted third-party (TTP) [22], or (iii) relying on a group of passengers who participates in the vehicle-sharing and server that manages vehicle-sharing system.

Security & Privacy Countermeasures Architectural countermeasures. The architectural design for carpooling is not well-described, and thus the literature considers two options: centralised system [22] and decentralised system [21]. For decentralised, blockchain-based ride-hailing platform for making matches between vehicle owners and potential passengers [21] has been proposed.

Technical countermeasures per functionality. The reviewed studies propose a few solutions for identity management, payment and location usage scenarios. For *identification*, pseudorandom identity assignment for using the system anonymously has been proposed in [22]. For payment, cryptocurrency-based payment [21] to preserve privacy of drivers and establish trust. Finally, *location privacy* [22,21] may be achieved by using location obfuscation (hiding the exact location by adding noise) [22], anonymity of location [22], and with cryptographical techniques to encrypt the location [22].

Cryptographic building blocks which supports carpooling is less versatile than used for smart parking and include tree Diffie-Hellman group key exchange protocol [22] or its variations, private set intersection protocol [22], Anonymous token [22], homomorphic probabilistic public-key encryption scheme (e.g., Paillier Cryptosystem [22]), and advanced encryption standard (AES) [22].

5.3 Connected Vehicles

The "connected vehicles" (also referred to as "internet of vehicles (IoV)") refers to the integration of vehicles, allowing them to exchange data with each other and with infrastructure.

The purposes of IoV can differ based on its setup and the enable features and include traffic management, safe driving, autonomous driving, road safety (intersection coordination, dynamic regulation of traffic lights), and infotainment [23].

People The connected vehicles are primarily based on such entities as: **edge devices** presented by roadside units (RSUs) [23,24] which communicate directly with vehicles in radio range and transmit messages to TAs or central servers; central server [23] navigation the cooperation between other entities; and vehicles [23,24]. Meanwhile, there are two key stakeholders. **Trusted Authority (TA)** [23] is a trusted third party responsible for the registration and management of vehicles within the network. TA should have high computational and communication capabilities for managing

vehicles' identities. Depending on the architecture, TA may be the only party who knows the true physical identity of the vehicle. **Vehicle user** uses one or more of the connected vehicles for transportation.

Privacy objectives [23]: (1) identity privacy – protecting user's physical identity from being leaked/disclosed; (2) location privacy – protection of user's location from being connected to a single user; (3) data privacy – protecting any personal data about the user from being disclosed.

Technical countermeasures per functionality. The main focus of the reviewed papers is on the authentication of entities that are connected to be a part of IoV. The state-of-the-art *authentication* measures include group and ring signatures to protect the vehicle's anonymity and preserve authenticity [24,25].

Privacy & Policies. In the case of usage group signatures, the policy of distributing and revoking distributed group keys should be established [24]. Usage of adaptive trust models [24] for enabling detection of 'unstable' dishonest behaviours.

5.4 Toll Collection

An (electronic) toll collection system enable automatic vehicle detection and classification in order to define either the pass through the toll is allowed and/or handle the charging of the vehicle based on the passing the toll [26,27].

People Toll entrance/exit station is a device located at each toll road entrance point. It is accessed, through some proximity protocol, by cars as they enter the road so as to get an entrance ticket [27]. **System server** is a central server which sets the parameters and cryptographic keys of the system and delivers them to all the other actors. It is accessed by exit stations to check that the entrance tickets handed in by cars are not fraudulent [27]. **Driver** is a person who is driving a car equipped with an on-board computer enabled with mobile Internet communications (like 4G or 5G), allowing it to communicate with the server and also some short-range system used to interact with entrance and exit stations [27].

Organisation design and strategy Purpose. Typically, electronic toll collection systems are used on the toll roads [26,27] in order to eliminate parking on highways to pay for the toll road usage and, as a result, decrease traffic congestion.

Information. The only piece of information manipulated in the toll collection system is an *entrance ticket* that is given to a vehicle and contains details of the toll road usage and the fee payment.

Process There are two steps in the toll collection that are considered in the reviewed papers. First, *privacy-preserving toll exit* should be assured. During the toll exit, the system does not learn the entrance station where the provided valid entrance ticket was generated [27] or get any information about the paid amount [27]. Second, *blind ticket issuance* on the toll entrance should be provided so that during the toll entrance, the system does not get any information about the involved vehicle nor about the generated entrance ticket [27].

Security & Privacy Countermeasures Architectural countermeasures. For security and privacy preservation, toll collection systems can be connected to vehicular ad hoc networks (VANET) [10,28]. Alternatively, blockchain-based automated toll-tax collection system [29,28] may be used.

Technical countermeasures per functionality. While vehicle identification is the primary task of toll collection system, the literature is focused on this functionality. It is proposed to leverage

automatic authentication based on RFID [26,29,30] or digital short-range communication (DSRC) detection equipment and high-resolution cameras [30].

Cryptographic building blocks which supports smart tollgates are RSA digital signature [27], blind signature [27], and oblivious transfer (e.g., price oblivious transfer protocol [27]).

6 Survey Research: Research Method

As the next step, the intelligent transportation sector companies were surveyed using a questionnaire to identify their level of information security and privacy management maturity. The questionnaire was developed using the identified from the literature review technologies and measures.

To define the state of intelligent transportation markets maturity (RQ₁), operation areas for ITSs (RQ₂) which information is manipulated and should be protected in ITSs (RQ₃), which information security and privacy standards (RQ₄), methods and procedures (RQ₅), tools and technologies (RQ₆) are used for protecting ITSs, we conducted an exploratory empirical survey study. This method was selected as our goal is to explore the phenomenon of assuring information security and privacy in intelligent transportation systems and gain insights into how it is done in the working market systems from the perspective of organisations that manage such ITSs. We selected a survey with a defined set of questions for a few reasons. First, it gives the respondents the possibility to answer the question without the restriction in time and allows them to use the help of colleagues or documentation, which contributes to the quality of the obtained data. Second, the questions in the written form can be translated to the respondent's native (or work) language if needed. Finally, the survey is intended to discover the facts about the used measures among the predefined range of options identified from the literature, so there is no need for elaborating questions and, thus, for other qualitative empirical research methods like interviews. In this section, we describe the details of the study setup (Sec. 6.1), data collection and analysis procedures (Sec. 6.2).

6.1 Study Setup

The study setup started by defining the profile of the targeted organisation and the profile of the organisation's representative. The targeted organisation should contribute to ITSs. Organisation may develop solutions, systems, and/or devices for ITSs and/or use intelligent transportation systems for their operations. The set of operation areas which we surveyed can be found in Table 3. Additionally, we were looking for organisations from the following operation areas: (electronic) toll collection, V2X communication, roadside unit operations, and ITS sensors. However, no organisations operating in these four areas and willing to participate in the survey were found in the selected regions.

In Estonia, an ITS network unites the intelligent transportation and logistic systems community⁶. Thus, the members of this network who meet the target profile were included in the initial pool. Additionally, we searched on the Internet and through partners the companies which also operate in the targeted areas. The initial pool of targeted organisations consists of 29 organisations in Estonia and 29 organisations in South Moravia, Czechia. We used several channels for approaching the targeted companies. The invitation emails were sent to the Estonian ITS network mailing list. At the same time, other organisations were approached through the publicly available email on the website of the organisation or using the direct contacts of the project partners in the targeted organisations. Additionally, if no response was received through email after two reminding follow-up emails, we looked for the public email of the targeted organisation employees (e.g., using the website of the organisation or LinkedIn). While the assumption of the study was that the targeted companies are mostly IT companies, and, therefore, most of the employees know English at least on the intermediate level, the emails were sent in two languages - the local language of the region (Czech for South Moravia and Estonian for Estonia) and English. The reason for the bilingual email was the intention to make it more appealing and increase the response rate.

The expected organisations' representatives who would answer the questionnaire should have a good understanding of the IT system (the key functionality and objectives) and be aware of

⁶ <https://its-estonia.com/>

Table 3: Operation areas of intelligent transportation systems (based on [1])

Name	Code	Total num. of partic.	Incl. in Estonia	Incl. in SM
Connected vehicles	CONV	6	2	4
Traffic management	TRAF	6	1	5
Parking service	PARK	5	2	3
Vehicle-sharing	VSHAR	3	2	1
Ride-hailing	RIDE	2	2	0
EV charging	CHARG	2	0	2
Autonomous vehicles	AV	3	3	0
Mobility analysis	MOBIL	1	1	0
Other (ITC services)	ITC	1	1	0
Total		15	8	7

internal organisational realities (incl. policies for the system support). Therefore, we approached people who occupy one of the following positions (or similar roles). In case the organisation manages the intelligent transportation system fully or maintains it, the targeted representatives were people in the position of chief technology officer (CTO), product owner/manager/analyst, system analyst, process owner/manager/analyst, software architect, information security officer (ISO), senior developer or system administrator (SysAdmin). In case the organisation is a transportation sector representative who does not have their own systems and uses only external systems (e.g., bought solutions or provided under the service-level agreement), the targeted representatives were people in the position of project manager, process owner/manager/analyst, IT manager, information security officer (ISO), chief information officer (CIO). As the questionnaire covers different aspects of an ITS, we expect the representative may need to consult with the system documentation, organisational guidelines, and/or colleagues.

The recruitment processes started on 10.March.2023, in South Moravia, and on 24.March.2023, in Estonia, and we closed the questionnaire on 1.June.2023. To get a more balanced dataset, we conducted the second round of recruitment in South Moravia between 1.September.2023 and 23.October.2023. With a response rate of 24 % and 27 %, we recruited representatives from 7 and 8 organisations in South Moravia and Estonia, respectively (15 organisations in total). The distribution of roles of the questionnaire respondents can be found in Table 4, and information about the profile of the surveyed organisation can be found in Figure 3.

6.2 Data Collection and Analysis

Before conducting the survey, we developed a questionnaire [31] based on the main research questions and findings from the prior literature review. The whole questionnaire was in English. Google Forms were used for delivering the survey to respondents as it allowed us to make branching in the questionnaire depending on the answers, making it easier for respondents to navigate. The questionnaire included questions related to general information about the company and its intelligent transportation system (see questions 1.1 – 1.7 in Appendix III related to RQ1, RQ2). The rest of the questionnaire was organised in four parts and roughly aligned to the four dimensions (organisational design, people and technological solutions, processes) based on ISACA’s BMIS [3], McCumber’s Cube [4] and RMIAS [5], and, thus, they aims to answer RQ3, RQ4, RQ5 and

Table 4: Study participants [2]

Role	Number of respond.	Role	Number of respond.
Software Developer	2	Product Manager	3
DevOps	1	Project Manager	2
ISO	2	Process Manager	1
CTO	2	Operations Specialist	1
SysAdmin	1		

Figure 3: Overview of the surveyed organisations [2]

RQ6. The mapping of the questions with the dimension of information assurance can be found in Appendix IV. The questionnaire ends with a section of follow-up questions about the survey which contributed to RQ5 and practices used for communicating security and privacy measures to stakeholders (e.g., *Which sources did you use to answer this survey?*, *How easy was it for you to find the information asked in this survey?*).

The questionnaire also includes a link to the glossary [31] so to help respondents with the technical terms used in the survey questions. The respondents were not limited in time for answering the questionnaire. Before distributing the questionnaire to the full pool of targeted companies, we piloted it with three respondents by asking them to provide feedback about the questions (e.g., *Were the questions understandable?*, *Did any of the questions seem irrelevant?*). The pilot did not reveal the need to update the questions and confirmed its usability for the targeted audience. Thus, it was used for surveying other respondents without any changes.

To analyse the data obtained through the questionnaire, one of the authors reviewed the answers to make sure each entry contained relevant answers and the provided information about the organisation corresponded to the initially targeted organisations. For the further analysis of answers to each question, from all the data entries removed the identifiers of the respondents (name, contact information) and the name of the organisation were removed so that each organisation was treated equally.

7 Survey Research: Results

Here we present the results of our study. Some of the respondents did not specify that their organisations operate primarily in South Moravia but in Czechia. However, as the respondents were selected considering their primary operation in South Moravia, the results present a comparison of two regions – South Moravia and Estonia.

7.1 Findings from the study setup phase.

The selected regions have a similar amount of companies operating with intelligent transportation systems. Noteworthy is the fact of the existence of an ITS networks in both regions. In Estonia, an ITS network unites the intelligent transportation and logistic systems (ITS) community ⁷ and in South Moravia, there is a Czech network of Intelligent transportation systems & services (ITS&S) ⁸. However, while in both of the regions, ITSs are in the development phase, the networks cover the number of organisations which do not develop or maintain ITSs but are interested in collaboration with ITS-oriented organisations. For example, the network includes members who provide general IT services, mapping solutions, or network solutions which could be used as a part of ITSs or for its setup.

7.2 ITSs maturity level

The first research question considers the level of ITSs maturity. Our study shows (see Figure 4a that most of the respondents (7 out of 15) consider their system an intelligent infrastructure system. Thus, respondents assessed that their system fully corresponds to the given definition of an ITS (“the advanced applications which without embodying intelligence as such aim to provide innovative services relating to different modes of transport and traffic management and enable various users to be better informed and make safer, more coordinated and ‘smarter’ use of transport networks”).

Figure 4: Overview of the surveyed organisations

Those respondents who assessed their system as not fully corresponding to the given definition of an intelligent transportation system, however, still assessed the system being partially an ITS (see value 1-3 in Fig. 4a). Thus, we conclude that their systems are less mature ITSs. One of the respondents assessed their system as not an ITS (see value 0 in Fig. 4a) there are transportation systems in the surveyed regions which would not be intelligent (ITSs of low maturity level), as the fact of their participation in the survey may be interpreted as the organisation's aim of developing the current system to ITSs.

⁷ <https://its-estonia.com/>

⁸ <http://www.sdt.cz/>

To additionally cross-check respondents' assessment of their organisations' system to be an ITS, we asked about the purpose of using the system. The results show (see Fig. 4b) that most of the surveyed organisations use the system(s) as both digital solutions for end-users and for exchanging data with external IT systems. Thus, we conclude that their systems are indeed ITSs (however, of different maturity levels).

7.3 Areas of using ITSs

The distribution of operation areas for the surveyed organisations can be found in Appendix II. The study shows that most of the surveyed organisations use ITSs for traffic management (6 out of 15), for operating connected vehicles (6 out of 15), and/or for smart parking (5 out of 15). Among eight Estonia-representing organisations, three organisations use ITSs for operating autonomous vehicles, and exactly two organisations operate in each of the following areas: smart parking, vehicle sharing, connected vehicles and ride-hailing. None of the surveyed organisations in Estonia operates in EV charging. As for organisations in South Moravia, 6 out of 7 organisations use ITSs for traffic management (three of which are also using ITSs for connected vehicles). None of the surveyed organisations in SM are involved in autonomous vehicle operation, ride-hailing, mobility analysis or providing ITC services. Finally, only four of the surveyed organisations' ITSs are used exclusively for one operation area, while others' ITSs are used in two (6 out of 15) or three (4 out of 15) areas.

7.4 P. People

To identify the sources of human-related security and privacy aspects, we asked the respondents about the stakeholders of their products and services of the intelligent transportation system. Under stakeholders, we mean "individuals, groups or organisations whose actions can influence or be influenced by the development and use of the system whether directly or indirectly" [32].

As a significant share of the surveyed organisations operates with connected vehicles, a *driver* is the most mentioned stakeholder (54%). The second most mentioned stakeholder is presented by *city government* (46%), followed by external *system providers* (under a service-level agreement) and internal *organisation's employees* (33%). The next go *parking service provider*, *trusted authority* and *passenger* (20%). *Time-stamping authority*, *parking or toll officer*, and *a defence agency* were indicated only by one organisation each. All the organisations (except for one) that operate with connected vehicles consider drivers to be stakeholders.

7.5 O. Organisational objectives, strategy and challenges

To understand the strategies of surveyed organisations about their ITSs, we asked respondents about the purposes of their ITSs and the challenges they face during the usage, development, and support of the ITSs. The study shows that five of the surveyed organisations enable on-demand mobility, and three aim to improve city services. Only two aim to decrease traffic congestion. Other ITSs aim to improve safety or urban traffic, reduce the cost of goods delivery, improve parking facilities, or make cities more livable overall (incl. environmental state). On the way to achieving its purposes, most organisations face the challenges of being interoperable with other systems and/or providers (9 out of 15) and perceive the lack of industry regulations and/or standards (7 out of 15). It is notable that interoperability is a challenge for organisations which has a varying number of external system integrations (1-2 external systems or more than 5), which means that it is a challenging task for more advanced and complex ITSs as much as for smaller ones. Fewer organisations are challenged by the expected level of security (highlighted by 6 out of 15 respondents), addressing user data privacy, security, and data minimisation (5 out of 15). Even fewer respondents point out that ensuring the balance between privacy and efficiency of the system is challenging for the organisation. Finally, 10 out of 15 organisations deal with at least 3 of the challenges mentioned in the survey.

Dimension		Attribute instances										
Category	Attribute	PA	Time-stamping authority	Defence	Parking/Toll Officer	Trusted Authority	Passenger	Parking Service Provider	System provider	Employee	City Government	Driver
P. People	PA	PA										
	OS	OS System purpose	Safety of urban traffic	Reduced cost for goods delivery	More livable cities	Improved parking facilities	Public transport control	Decreased the traffic congestion	Improved city services	On-demand mobility		
O. Organization	OS	OS Challenges	Hetero- geneous network	Resource constrained devices	High system quality expectations	Privacy vs efficiency	User data privacy and security	Data minimisation	Expected level of security	Lack of industry regulations	Interoperability	
	OC	OC regulations	EU 2019/2144	EU 2018/858	ITS Directive	UN R155	GDPR	ISO 27001				
C. Sec. & Privacy Counter-measures	OC	OC standards	NIST SP	Other standards from ISO/IEC 27000-series	E-ITS	ETSI standards series	Cyber Security Act in Czechia					
	OI	OI (Information types)	Information about roadside units	Other information	Information about passenger	Information about transactions	Aggregated information	Information about driver	Information about vehicle			
C. Sec. & Privacy Counter-measures	CP	CP (Practices & Policies)	Normal best practices	Penetration testing	Threat modelling	Security Lifecycle	Risk management	Security framework	Security strategy			
	CE	CE Trainings Employees	Reading news about security issues	Cyber hygiene trainings	Trainings for raising awareness about security threats	Data protection trainings						
CT	CE	CE Sources For Survey	Documentation	Colleagues	Knowledge of the organisation	Knowledge of the system						
	CT	CT Crypto	Homomorphic encryption	Zero- Knowledge Proof	Oblivious pseudorandom function (OPRF)	Blind signature	Oblivious transfer protocol	Trusted execution environment (TEE)	Private set intersection (PSI)	Hash-based message authentic. codes	Elliptic curve cryptography	Diffie-Hellman group key exchange
Pr. Processes	CT	CT Secure Communication	Custom asymmetric encryption	IPSec protocol	Other secured communication protocol	Customer end-to-end encryption	VPN solution					
	CT	CT Architectural Measures	Blockchain- based system	Multi-party computation (MPC)	Storage of anolated data	Secret-sharing	Anonymous authentication	Storage of personal data on the data subject device	Securing data in transit			
Pr. Processes	CT	CT Authent. & Access Control	Biometric- based authentication	Pseudo- random identity assignment	Anonymous credential system	Attribute-based credentials and access control	RFID authentication	2-factor authentication	Role-based access control	Public Key Infrastructure		
	CT	CT UC Navigation & Routing	Location obfuscation	Third-party navigation system	Privacy- preserving navigation systems		Token-based payment					
Pr. Processes	CT	CT UC Payment	Anonymous payment	Automated payment using smart contract	Cash	Direct carrier billing (DCB)		Card-based payment				
	CT	CT UC Location Based Search	Private information retrieval	Hashmap storing of parking slot/toll/vehicle locations	Search based on the exact location							
Pr. Processes	CT	CT UC Reserv. Document Creation	Blind signature	Anonymous reservation	Presenting proof-of-knowledge							
	PrL	PrL Principles for System Development	Privacy-related testing and verification	Usage of sensor devices which have built-in security measures	Data minimisation	Secure programming	Privacy by design					
PrU	PrL	PrL System Support Network	Firewall	VLANs	Security/incident and event management systems (SEIM)	Intrusion detection system	Behavioural analytics system	Vulnerability scanner	Network traffic analyser			
	PrU	PrU Use Cases	Pass/reservation document creation	Navigation or routing	Payment	Location-based search						

Cell colour mapping: 0 3 6 14
 (by number of supporting responses)

Text colour mapping: measure1 (black) - state-of-the-art measure
 measure2 (grey) - other

Figure 5: Distribution of information security and privacy measures usage by the surveyed organisations [2]

Figure 6: Overview of the surveyed organisations [2]

O.1. Information used in ITSs In order to achieve its objectives while being constrained by the challenges, let us have a look at what kind of information is manipulated in intelligent infrastructure systems (see RQ3). Overall, the information can be grouped into seven groups: related to vehicle, driver, parking/ride/toll, passenger, roadside ITS components, aggregated, and other (internally used data about the platform or environment). *Vehicle*-related information is mostly manipulated (by 11 out of 15 organisations) and includes the vehicle’s location, state details, identity and speed of surrounding vehicles. *Driver*-, *parking/ride/toll*-related, and *aggregated* information are the second most manipulated by the surveyed organisations (7 out of 15). *Driver*-related information includes data about the driver’s identity, location, transactions and payment details. *Parking/ride/toll*-related information includes data about available parking spaces or tolls, parking/ride/toll-transactions, and such information is naturally collected by organisations which operate with smart parking, ride-hailing, and EV charging. *Aggregated* data based on the transactions history is manipulated by almost the same organisations that operate with parking/ride/toll transactions. *Passenger*-related information includes data about passengers’ identity, transactions, payments or anonymous transaction validation and is manipulated only by three organisations that conduct either traffic management or ride-hailing. Information about *roadside ITS units* (incl. traffic lights) are used only by two organisations which operate with connected vehicles. Other kinds of information about the environment are manipulated only by two organisations which operate with autonomous vehicles or mobility analysis.

The study shows that almost half of the representatives of organisations that manipulate driver-related data do not consider the driver as a stakeholder. Moreover, none of the representatives who indicated manipulation of passenger-related data considered passengers stakeholders. Such results may be either a sign of a lack of representatives’ awareness about the situation or a sign of neglecting actors and their interests regardless of the use of their data. Another finding of the study is that the usage of data about roadside ITS components naturally depends on the city government as a stakeholder (as most probably, they are the managing authority of roadside units).

O.2. Standards and Regulations The questions about regulations and standards are among the least answered (5 and 4 out of 15 respondents answered as “I don’t know” to the respective questions). The respondents who could not answer the questions occupy exclusively technical positions (software developers, CTO, SysAdmin and operations specialist). According to ten responses, there are six security or privacy-related legislation and/or regulations which affect the surveyed organisations: *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)*, *European Union directive 2010/40/EU (7 July 2010)* (i.e. ITS Directive), *UNECE regulation No 155 Cyber security and cyber security management system* (from 2020) (i.e. UN R155), *Regulation (EU) 2019/2144 of the European Parliament and of the Council* (i.e. EU 2019/2144), *Regulation (EU) 2018/858 of the European Parliament and of the Council* (i.e. EU 2018/858), and *NIS2 directive*. GDPR affects all

the respondents (both in SM and Estonia). UN R155 is mentioned by three organisations (in total, from SM and Estonia). The regulations EU 2019/2144 and EU 2018/858 are highlighted by only one Estonian company. The NIS2 directive is also mentioned by only one organisation from SM. It is interesting to note that only respondents occupying positions which require an overall view of the system and its infrastructure (as an information security officer and DevOps) highlight regulations other than GDPR (which is known for a wider audience).

There are six security standards followed by the surveyed organisations: *Předpis 181/2014 Sb. (zákon o kybernetické bezpečnosti)* (Cyber Security Act in Czechia), *ISO/IEC 27001*, *ETSI standards series*, *other standards from ISO/IEC 27000-series*, *Eesti infoturbestandard* (Estonian Information Security Standard, i.e. E-ITS), and *NIST Special Publications* (NIST SP). 4 out of 7 of the surveyed organisations in SM mentioned Cyber Security Act in Czechia (while one company from South Moravia, which claims that no standards are applicable for them). In SM, 6 out of 7 organisations follow ISO/IEC 27001, and 5 out of 7 follow ETSI standards. Two organisations (both in SM) additionally follow other standards from ISO/IEC 27000-series except for ISO/IEC 27001. One SM organisation additionally follows NIST SP (which is probably due to operating globally, predominantly in the EU). Among Estonian organisations (representatives of which are able to provide the answer), ISO/IEC 27001 is the main security standard followed by 3 out of 4 organisations. One organisation in Estonia follows only E-ITS, which is, however, compliant with ISO/IEC 27001.

7.6 C. Countermeasure for Information Security and Privacy Assurance

Here, we describe the results of our study on countermeasures used by the surveyed organisations for assuring information security and privacy. The countermeasures are divided into three groups – organisational policies & practices, people-oriented training & education, and technological measures.

C.1. Policies & Practices There are six practices used by the surveyed organisations: penetration testing, following a selected risk management framework, following a selected security framework, following a national (cyber) security strategy, threat modelling, and security development lifecycle. Overall, in the selected regions, following a selected risk management framework and security framework along with a national (cyber) security strategy are the mostly used (6 out of 15). Comparing the two regions, South Moravian companies are leading in terms of the number of used organisational countermeasures. For example, 2 out of 7 respondents answered that their organisation follows all the six mentioned different practices. All SM organisations have at least one security practice in place, while the most practised is following a national (cyber) security strategy, followed by using selected risk management and a selected security framework. In contrast, in Estonia, two organisations' representatives (2 out of 8) claim that there are no practices or policies followed in the organisations. Based on the study, organisations in Estonia have at most 2 security practices in place. Following a selected risk management framework and a selected security framework are the most popular among Estonian organisations, while no respondent from Estonia has mentioned penetration testing.

In addition to the mentioned security and privacy practices, we studied principles used during the ITS development and support activities. *Secure programming* and *privacy by design* are the most commonly used across the surveyed organisations (33%). However, the prevalence of principles differs from region to region. For example, data minimisation is as much used in Estonia as secure programming (38% of Estonian companies), while data minimisation is used by only 1 SM organisation. In contrast, privacy by design is the mostly used principle in SM (57%), followed by secure programming, privacy-related testing and verification, together with the usage of sensor devices which have built-in security measures (29%). In Estonia, privacy by design, privacy-related testing and verification, and usage of sensor devices which have built-in security measures are

scarce (13%). And 25% of Estonian organisations even indicated not using any of the proposed (or similar) principles.

As an additional way of assessing organisational countermeasures and their practising, we assessed respondents' knowledge about their awareness of the situation. Thus, we asked respondents to assess the level of their ITS security, which sources they used for answering the questionnaire, and how easy it was to find the asked in the study information.

The self-assessment of the *ITS security level* resulted in the consensus among SM respondents in assessing their ITSs as *secure, but could be improved*. 37% of Estonian organisations consider their ITSs *somewhat secure, should be improved*, while another 50% assesses the ITSs as better ones (*secure, but could be improved*). Finally, one Estonian organisation seems to have either better practises of security or better communication with employees, so the representative indicates that their ITS is *secured according to up-to-date measures and considering relevant threats*.

Finally, 5 respondents indicated that to answer the questionnaire, they used documentation (including manuals, guidelines, technical documentation, etc.) or consulted with colleagues, while others used only their personal knowledge of the system and/or organisation. Thus, the study shows that overall, the level of awareness about security and privacy in South Moravia and Estonia and the level of communication of the relevant knowledge is quite high with respect to the provided answers.

C.2. Training As the organisation's employees and intelligent transportation system users are the most numerous groups of stakeholders, in our study, we asked respondents about security and privacy training established for these two stakeholder groups.

In our study, we mentioned four kinds of training for system users, which differ in their value impact on the information security of the ITSs. Thus, *introducing the privacy policy during the first onboarding to the system* is scaled to the lowest (value 1), followed by *introducing the information security measure of the system that concerns their data or behaviour* (value 2) and *regular reminders about privacy policy aspects* (value 3). The highest value is given to *phishing training* (value 4) as it requires extra effort and contributes to the users' general knowledge and cyber hygiene. Similarly to the situation with policies, the practice of security and privacy-related training for end users is more established among SM organisations. Almost all SM representatives (except for one) indicate introducing the privacy policy during the first onboarding to the system; four representatives also mentioned regular reminders and/or introducing the information security measure. Additionally, two organisations conduct phishing training for system users. Meanwhile, two (out of six) Estonian organisations' representatives indicate that they do not conduct any training for system users. All other Estonian organisations educate users about privacy policy, and only one introduced the information security measure of the system that concerns their data or behaviour. Based on the survey, none of the Estonian ITS-related organisations conduct user phishing training.

In our study, we mentioned three kinds of training for employees – data protection training (related to data privacy), training for raising awareness about security threats, and cyber hygiene training. Overall, *data protection training* and *training for raising awareness about security threats* are the most used types for educating organisations' employees. The representatives of SM organisations mentioned at least one training type per organisation. Two of the Estonian organisations' representatives mention that they do not have any training in place. Cyber hygiene training is less popular in SM (1 out of 7, 14%) than in Estonia (3 out of 8, 37%). Also, one Estonian organisation mentioned reading news about security issues as a type of education for employees.

C.3. Technological countermeasures The questions in the study about technological countermeasures were based on the state-of-the-art measures found during the literature review and presented in Appendix I. Additionally, the answer options are populated with more commonly used,

not state-of-the-art, ITSs measures to capture at least any data for maturing intelligent transportation systems.

C.3.1. Architectural measures The most commonly used architectural countermeasures across regions are *securing data in transit*, followed by *storing sensitive personal data on the data subject device*, *anonymous authentication*, and, finally, *secret-sharing*. None of the respondents indicated using blockchain-based systems or multi-party computation (MPC) in their ITSs. All the respondents indicated usage of at least one of the mentioned architectural measures, while some highlighted the usage of two or three measures per organisation (two and one organisation in SM and Estonia, respectively).

C.3.2. Use case-oriented measures The first use case we investigated in our study is ***authentication and access control***. Except for the mentioned in Appendix I state-of-the-art countermeasures, the questionnaire includes the options of role-based access control (RBAC), public key infrastructure (PKI), and 2-factor authentication (2FA). The study shows that in the selected regions, there is a tendency to use non-state-of-the-art measures for authentication and access control. 85% of SM-based organisations (6 out of 7) use RBAC, PKI or both. 2FA is the second most used measure in both regions, along with PKI in Estonia and RBAC in SM. Among the state-of-the-art measures, the only used measures in the Estonian region are *anonymous credentials* and *attribute-based credentials and access control* (25% and 13% respectively). Also, one Estonian company mentioned the usage of MSISDN (phone number) for authentication which can be an instance of pseudorandom identity assignment. In SM, *RFID authentication* is the most used state-of-the-art measure used by 43% of organisations (3 out of 7), followed by *attribute-based credentials and access control* (29 %, 2 out of 7). *Anonymous credential system* and *pseudorandom identity assignment* are used by only 14% of SM organisations (1 out of 7). Finally, no surveyed organisations use biometric-based authentication. Except for one, all South Moravian organisations use at least 2 of the mentioned measures (but not more than 4), while Estonian organisations use at least 1 and at most 3.

Next, we studied the measure for establishing ***secure communication***. Overall, TLS is the mostly used measure across two regions (86%) and in each region separately (80% in SM and 63% in Estonia), followed by VPN solutions (60% overall). In Sm, the mentioned measures are equally used and are followed by IPsec protocol and customer end-to-end encryption (43%). Custom asymmetric encryption and some other secured communication protocols are used only by one SM organisation (14%). In contrast, IPsec is not used by any Estonian organisation, while VPN solutions and other secured communication protocols are the second most used (38%) after TLS, followed by customer end-to-end encryption and custom asymmetric encryption (13%). Similarly to the previous countermeasure group, all the SM organisations use at least 2 of the mentioned measures (but not more than 5), while Estonian organisations use from 1 to 3.

The following three groups of measures are functionality-specific and, thus, irrelevant for some of the surveyed organisations due to their operation nature. The state-of-the-art suggested only two measures for ***navigation and routing***, namely *privacy-preserving navigation systems* and *location obfuscation*. The former is a leading and the only measure among the three organisations in SM which have the respective functionality. Among three organisations in Estonia with navigation functionality, each uses a different measure – either the one of the proposed or a third-party navigation system.

Similarly to navigation-related measures, the state-of-the-art suggested only two measures for ***payment***, namely *anonymous payment* and *automated payment using smart contract*. We additionally included solutions of *card-based payment* and *token-based payment* that are commonly used but not mentioned in the literature. The study shows that none of the state-of-the-art measures for payment are used by 6 organisations that have payment functionality in the selected regions. All the SM organisations (2 out of 2) use card-based payment and token-based payment side by side.

One SM organisation additionally mentioned using cash. In Estonia, among four organisations, the card-based payment is leading (75%). One such Estonian organisation use direct carrier billing (DCB) additionally. One organisation use exclusively token-based payment.

The **location-based search** is the next studied functionality. This functionality is used separately from the navigation and routing to search slots, tolls or vehicles at the specific location. The literature proposed three measures – *private information retrieval* (PIR), *hashmap storing* of parking slot/toll/vehicle locations, and *a search based on the exact location*. Among the three Estonian organisations, the later one is the most used (by all the organisations). Hashmap storing is an additional measure one organisation uses along with a search based on the exact location. Any surveyed organisation in SM does not use hashmap storing, while PIR and search based on the exact location are used equally as I/O counting.

None of the surveyed organisations indicated having the functionality of **pass/reservation document creation**. Therefore, there are no results of the state-of-the-art measures usage related to this functionality.

C.3.3. Cryptographic measure The question about cryptographic measures usage was as challenging as one about security practices and policies (7 out of 15 respondents could not answer the question). Among three SM organisations, there is no clear preference for cryptographic measures. RSA digital signature is used by 2 organisations (67% of respondents who were able to answer). Trusted execution environment (TEE), private set intersection (PSI), elliptic curve cryptography, Diffie-Hellman group key exchange, and hash-based message authentication codes are equally used. The results show that each SM organisation uses from one to four different cryptographic measures side by side. In Estonia, RSA signature is a clearly leading measure (used by 75% among four respondents), followed by Diffie-Hellman group key exchange (50%) and elliptic curve cryptography (25%). The results show that none of the other state-of-the-art measures are used.

Additionally, we asked respondents about their organisations' intentions of using post-quantum cryptography. Among those who were able to answer (66%), only one organisation from SM indicated intention of employing such technologies within 1 - 3 years. Also, one organisation from each region indicated they were considering employing such technologies but not earlier than 3 years after answering the survey.

C.3.4. Other The questionnaire about the technological countermeasure finishes with an open-ended question to let respondents share their knowledge without being restricted to a specific type of countermeasure (*What are the other security- or privacy-preserving technologies used in your intelligent transportation system which was not mentioned?*). Respondents highlighted extra countermeasures from the groups of practices & policies (namely, *security by design*, *physical separation* (closed protected workspace), *network separation* (maximum use of city-owned cable net)), cryptographic measures (namely, *symmetric cryptography*), oriented to the use case of network connection (*DNS over TLS*, and *DNSSEC*). Additionally, time-stamping was mentioned, which should contribute to the assuring traceability and audibility of the system (another use-case oriented measure which was not explicitly mentioned in the literature except the existence of time-stamping authority as a stakeholder).

7.7 Pr. Processes

Here, we present the results of the study about the processes in organisations related to the intelligent transportation system lifecycle and support.

Most of the surveyed organisations have a development team that is fully responsible for the system, its support and development (73%) and, thus, holds the sole responsibility and control over the ITSs. Only 13% of organisations (2 organisations) have a small development/support team who

in-house manage the system developed by an external service provider. And only one company (7%) uses a ready-to-use solution, which the system provider continuously updates. Thus, in both SM and Estonia, ITSs are rather centralised and managed mainly by one organisation (i.e., owner) rather than used as a service or managed collaboratively.

As the involvement in the system lifecycle does not differ much across the organisations, we cannot conclude that it affects the dynamics of the systems (i.e. how much the system changes over time). Across the regions during the last 5 years, 27% of organisations have a new system that has been developed separately from the old system, and as many organisations (27%) made significant changes in the system and its components. Even though a major part of organisations highlighted interoperability as a challenging task, no organisations had to make major changes in the system and its components due to the integration with external system(s). Other 20% of organisations make minor changes to the main functionality and actively support the existing system. Only 20% of organisations make major changes to the main functionality and actively support and develop the existing system. Finally, none of the respondents indicated that their ITSs had not changed at all during the last 5 years, which confirms the fact that ITSs are in the active development phase and are establishing in the selected regions (which is also highlighted by the respectively low number of active organisations on the market). Comparing the dynamic of ITSs in regions, the results show that, in SM, organisations are more tend to develop a new system separately from the old system (43% in SM over 25% in Estonia).

The research on how security and privacy assurance are integrated into the existing process is the major interest of our study. The results show a significant part of organisations in the surveyed regions update their ITSs with regularly with ad-hoc security patches regularly (40%) or security patches (27%). Based on this, we conclude that such organisations have an average level of security integration in the system lifecycle. Meanwhile, only a few organisations (20%) have a dedicated security team continuously working on security and privacy measures, mainly representatives of the SM region. A promising sign of the organisations' awareness of the importance of security is that none indicated that they assumed their systems were secure as they were launched and avoided updating them.

In regard to system support, in the study, we focused on network security measures. The presented options were the following: intrusion detection system, security incident and event management systems (SEIM), behavioural analytics system, network traffic analyser, and vulnerability scanner. More than half of the representatives (60%) indicated this type of measure either as not applicable or could not provide an answer. Among the given answers, *network traffic analyser* is the mostly used measure (83%). *Intrusion detection systems*, *behavioural analytics systems*, and *vulnerability scanners* are equally used by 50% of respondents. Two organisations use *security incident and event management systems* (33%). Also, one organisation uses firewalls and VLANs. All of the obtained answers indicate that if organisations opt for using network protection, they use at least two different measures for that. Also, as firewalls was not mentioned as an option in the survey, we assume that there may be more than one organisation among the sample that use firewalls for the network protection, but some respondents did not mention it (and some other technologies) due to not willing to provide such details or not awareness.

7.8 Other findings based on the study results

While employees of exclusively technical positions did not answer the questions about security and privacy-related regulations and standards, we conclude that there is a lack of information security countermeasures for security policies and training which would communicate to all the stakeholders existing organisational limitations in terms of regulations and/or training on this matter.

Statistical analysis. We performed a statistical data analysis to determine whether there are any dependencies between the usage of different information security and privacy measures based on

the survey results. Each survey answer provided by an organisation representative is considered a separate data entry. Each question in the survey contains a limited set of answers. Therefore, each measure about which it was asked in the survey corresponds to a categorical (nominal or ordinal) data variable. An example of an ordinal variable is the level of security integration into the system lifecycle. An example of a nominal variable is the region of operation or respondent's position. As a result, each data entry consists of a set of categorical variables. During the data preparation, some nominal categorical variables were split into a set of variables so that each variable describes a single answer, not a set nominal value. For example, while in the original dataset, there is one variable corresponding to challenges faced by a company and the value is a set of challenges, in the analysed dataset, we split each challenge into a separate variable (e.g., `chall_HighQualExpect` and `chall_Heterogeneous`) which describes the fact of presence (value=1) or absence (value=0) of the challenge for the organisation.⁹

As the dataset consists of categorical and ordinal data, we use Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (r_s), which measures a monotonic association between two variables [33]. Table 5 describes variables with statistically significant high correlation coefficients with significance level $p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$.

The strongest correlation ($r_s = 1$) is found between the following variables: `practicesPolicies_5` and `practicesPolicies_6`, `chall_HighQualExpect` and `Pr_systemSupport_network_2`, and `stakeholders_1` and `practicesPolicies_1`. The first correlation corresponds to the causation: `policy_6` (Security Development Lifecycle) causes `policy_5` (Threat model), as threat modelling is the mandatory building block of the Security Development Lifecycle. The strong correlation between having a challenge of high expectations from ITSs quality (`chall_HighQualExpect`) and the practice of using security incident and event management systems (SEIM, `Pr_systemSupport_network_2`) can be explained by the fact that SEIM helps to improve ITSs quality and supports maintaining system security during incidents. Finally, the correlation between having Trusted Authority (`stakeholders_1`) as a stakeholder and using penetration testing (`practicesPolicies_1`) may refer to the organisation's awareness of security vulnerabilities, which may originate from internal management of the system (incl. identity management and system development). Thus, such organisations acknowledge both the need to review their system with penetration testing and outsourcing identity management to a Trusted Authority.

A weaker correlation ($0.85 < r_s \leq 0.95$) is found between three variable pairs. First, as we pointed out before, almost all the organisations having payment functionality use a card-based payment method ($r_s = 0.86$), which may refer to the need to have its payment option when having an intelligent transportation system in the selected regions. Second, the strong correlation between end-to-end encryption and privacy by design is expected, as using end-to-end encryption is one of the foundational principles of privacy by design. Therefore, $r_s = 1$ is expected to be present to characterise the causation. Not having causation in the dataset questions the correctness of the answers of some respondents. So, either the organisations claim to assure privacy by design but do not follow all its principles, or there's a lack of respondents' awareness about the privacy practices they follow. Third, the correlation between the usage of a selected security framework (`practicesPolicies_3`) and training for raising awareness about security threats (`trainingsEmployees_2`) confirms the actual usage of some security frameworks by the respondents as usually such frameworks (e.g., NIST cybersecurity framework) prescribe training employees about security risks and threats.

An even weaker but still significant correlation ($0.75 < r_s \leq 0.85$) is found between four variable pairs. First, the higher the number of end-users of ITSs, the higher the tendency to store sensitive personal data on the data subject device (as an architectural solution). Second, the ITSs,

⁹ The list of analysed variables and their mapping to the survey questions together with the full list of significant correlation values can be found in supplementary materials in [31].

Table 5: Correlation between variables collected through the survey (p-value ≤ 0.05) [2]

Variable 1	Variable 1 description	Variable 2	Variable 2 description	r_s
practices Policies_5	Used practice and policy: Threat modelling	practices Policies_6	Followed practice and policy: Security Development Lifecycle	1
chall_HighQual Expect	Challenge: High expectations from ITS quality	Pr_systemSupport_network_2	Followed system support practice: Security incident and event management systems	1
stakeholders_1	Stakeholder: Trusted Authority	practices Policies_1	Followed practice and policy: Penetration testing	1
architMeasures_2	Arhitectural measure: Anonymous authentication	C_authent AccessControl_8	Authentication measure: Anonymous credential system	1
hasPayment	Has payment	C_UC_payment_1	Card-based payment	0.866
practices Policies_3	Used practice and policy: Selected security framework	trainings Employees_2	Trainings for raising awareness about security threats	0.873
C_secure Communication_5	Customer end-to-end encryption	P_principles_systemDevelopment_2	Privacy by design	0.853
C_authent AccessControl_8	Authentication measure: Anonymous credential system	C_UC_location BasedSearch_3	Search based on the exact location	0.829
endUsers	Number of end users (range)	architMeasures_3	Storage of sensitive personal data on the data subject device	0.82
stakeholders_3	Stakeholder: Driver	practices Policies_3	Followed practice and policy: Selected security framework	0.764
standards_2	Used standard: ISO 27001	practices Policies_4	Followed practice and policy: National security strategy	0.763
hasLocationBased Search	Having the functionality of location-based search	chall_UserPriSec	Challenge: Addressing data privacy and security	0.756

which consider a driver as one of the stakeholders, tend to follow some selected security framework. Third, the following national security strategy is correlated with following the standard ISO/IEC 27001. Finally, having the functionality of location-based search correlates with the challenge of addressing data privacy and security.

To sum up, the statistical data analysis of the survey dataset shows that the used reference model of information security and privacy assurance in the intelligent systems (Fig. 7) is able to depict cross-dimensional dependencies between the categories of information security and privacy

measures. As a result, the frameworks can be used for cross-checking the measures' implementation across different aspects of organisations.

Limitations. There may be bias in the awareness about the ITS security state across the SM organisations as most of the organisations had some cooperation projects on cybersecurity with the authors from South Moravia, and thus, such organisations may have more interest and expertise in security assurance compared to surveyed Estonian organisations with which there was no previous collaboration.

There is a threat to the study's construct validity. The obtained study results may have differed if the respondents were explicitly instructed that they were encouraged to use organisational supplementary materials when answering the questions (e.g., organisational guidelines, documentation and consultation with colleagues).

Acknowledgements This study is supported by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101087529. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Appendix I. State-of-the-Art Measures of Information Security and Privacy Assurance in ITS

Table 6: State-of-the-Art Attributes for Technological Countermeasures

Type of countermeasure		Countermeasures					
Use case-oriented	Architectural	Blockchain- based system	Anonymous authentication	Storage of sensitive personal data on the data subject device	Secret- sharing	Multi-party computation (MPC)	Securing data in transit
	Authenti- cation & Access control	Anonymous credential system	Attribute- based control	credentials and access	RFID authenti- cation	Pseudo- random identity assignment	Biometric- based authentica- tion
	Secure communi- cation	TLS protocol	IPSec protocol	VPN solution	Other secured communi- cation protocol	Customer end-to-end encryption	Custom asymmetric encryption
	Navigation and routing	Privacy- preserving navigation systems		Location obfuscation			
	Payment	Automated payment using smart contract		Anonymous payment			
	Location- based search	Hashmap storing of parking slot/ toll/ vehicle locations		Location- based search	Search based on the exact location		
	Pass document creation	Blind signature	Anonymous reservation	Presenting proof-of- knowledge			
Cryptographic		RSA digital signature	Homomor- phic encryption	Zero- Knowledge Proof	Oblivious pseudo- random function (OPRF)	Trusted execution environment (TEE)	Private set intersection (PSI)
		Blind signature	Elliptic curve cryptography	Diffie-Hell- man group key exchange	Hash-based message authentica- tion codes	Oblivious transfer protocol	

Table 8: State-of-the-Art attributes: People, Processes and Organisation dimensions

Dimension		Attributes				
People	Actor	Driver	Passenger	City Government	Trusted Authority (who issues credentials)	
		Time-stamping authority	Organisation employee	Parking Service Provider	System provider (based on SLA)	
Organisation	Purpose of ITS usage	Decreasing the traffic congestion	Resolving the problem of air pollution	Improvement of the city services	Improved management of parking facilities	Enabling on-demand mobility
		Optimising driver's time spent on parking	Optimisation of parking spaces usage	Preventing unauthorized occupation of spots		
	Challenges	Addressing data privacy and security of users' data in order to prevent identity and trajectory leakage		The balance between privacy and efficiency of the system		Heterogeneous network
		Absence or lack of industry regulations and/or standards		Providing the expected level of system security before the system is launched		Following the data minimization principle
		High expectations from such system quality characteristics (e.g., platform independence, OS independence)		Absence of national strategy for developing smart environments	Resource- constrained devices usage	Interoperability with other systems and/or providers
	Legislation & regulations	General Data Protection Regulation (EU GDPR)	European Union directive 2010/40/EU (7 July 2010)	Consumer protection directives 2019/770 and 2019/771	UNECE regulation No 155 Cyber security and cyber security management system (from 2020)	
	Standards	ISO 27001	ISO 27002	Other standards from ISO/IEC 27000-series	NIST Special Publications (e.g. NIST SP 800-39, NIST SP 800-37)	ETSI standards series (e.g. ETSI TS 102 941, 102 731)
	Information	Driver's identity	Driver's location	Driver's transactions history	Driver's payment details	Available parking spaces
		Available tolls	Passenger's identity	Passenger's transactions history	Passenger's payment details	Vehicle's location
		Vehicle's state details	Vehicle's identity	Parking/ Ride/ Toll transaction		
Process	System support	Intrusion detection system	Security incident and event management systems (SEIM)	Behavioural analytics system	Network traffic analyser	Vulnerability scanner
	ITS in the business process	Navigation/ routing	Payment	Location-based search	pass/reservation document creation	

Appendix II. Questionnaire (shortened)

General questions about the company

In this section, we ask you to fill in general information about your company, so that researchers are able to define the sector profile of your company.

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be found in supplementary materials in [31].

- 1.1. What is your organisation's name?
- 1.2. What is your position/role in the organization?
- 1.3. Where does your company primarily operate?
- 1.4. For which purposes does your company use IT system(s)?
- 1.5. Would you call the system used in your company "an intelligent transportation system"?
- 1.6. In which area does your company primarily operate?
- 1.7. How many active end-users does your digital solution have in the selected region?

Section "Organisation"

The following questions are related to the organisation's design and strategy. The questions aim to define how the organisation's strategy guides the processes based on the strategic objectives, how the organisational design and strategy itself are guided by the external factors (e.g., legal and regulatory provisions), how the organisation's structure peoples by the established culture towards information security, and how the organisation's strategy drives the architecture of the technical security measures.

- 2.1. What is the main objective of your intelligent transportation system?
- 2.2. How much is your company involved in the lifecycle of your intelligent transportation system?
- 2.3. How much has your system changed during the last 5 years?
- 2.4. With how many external systems is your system integrated?
- 2.5. What are the challenges your company faces during the usage/development/support of your intelligent transportation system?
- 2.6. What kind of information is used within your intelligent transportation system?
- 2.7. Which security or privacy-related legislation and/or regulations affect your intelligent transportation system?
- 2.8. Which cyber/information security standard(s) does your organisation follow?

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 1"

The following questions are related to the stakeholders of your intelligent transportation system (ITS) as well as policies & practices your organisation use.

- 3.1. Who are the stakeholders of your products/services the intelligent transportation system?
- 3.2. What are the practices and policies used for assuring information security and/or privacy management in your company?
- 3.3. How much security development is integrated into your system lifecycle?
- 3.4. Which information security and privacy training are established for your system users?
- 3.5. Which information security and privacy training are established for the employees in your organisation?

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 2"

The following questions are related to the technological profile of your organisation.

- 4.1. Which of the following architectural measures are used in your intelligent transportation system?
- 4.2. Which technologies are used in your intelligent transportation system for authentication and access control?
- 4.3. Which measures are used in your intelligent transportation system for secure communication between parties?
- 4.4. Which cryptographic measures are used in your intelligent transportation system?

Section “Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: System functionality”

This section contains question about functionality-specific measures in you intelligent infrastructure system.

4.5.1. Do you have navigation/routing functionality in your intelligent transportation system?

4.5.2. Which technologies are used in your intelligent transportation system for navigation/routing?

4.6.1. Do you have payment functionality in your intelligent transportation system?

4.6.2. Which technologies are used in your intelligent transportation system for payment?

4.7.1. Do you have location-based search in your intelligent transportation system?

4.7.2. Which technologies are used in your intelligent transportation system for parking slot/toll/vehicle search?

4.8.1. Do you have functionality of pass/reservation document creation in your intelligent transportation system?

4.8.2. Which technologies are used in your intelligent transportation system for ticket generation, parking or ride reservation?

Section “Security and Privacy measures. Other”

4.9. What are the other security- or privacy-preserving technologies used in your intelligent transportation system which was not mentioned?

4.10. Do you consider employing post-quantum cryptography in the future in your intelligent infrastructure system?

Section “Security and Privacy measures. Part 4: Processes”

The following questions are related to processes established for managing your intelligent infrastructure system.

5.1. Which of the following principles are used during your system development/support?

5.2. Which network security measures are used for your intelligent transportation system support?

Follow-up questions about this survey

How would you assess the level of your information system security?

Which sources did you use to answer this survey?

How easy was it for you to find the information asked in this survey?

(Optional) Feedback or comments regarding the survey Were the questions understandable? Should some questions be changed, redrafted, or should something be added? Did any of the questions seem irrelevant? Do you have any suggestions for improving the survey?

Appendix III. Mapping FISP with the questionnaire

Dimension	Category	Attribute	Questions from the questionnaire
P. People	PA. Actors	Actors, stakeholders, entities	3.1; Follow-up questions
		Goals, tasks, motives	
	PR. Relationships	Relationships and dependencies between actors	-
O. Organisation	OS. Strategy	Purpose for the system usage, org. design & strategy	2.1,
		Challenges to address	2.5
	OC. Formal Constraints	Legislation, regulation, standard	2.7-2.8
	OI. Information Involved	Type of information used	-
		How the information is manipulated	2.6
		Security criteria	-
	Privacy objectives	-	
C. Sec. & Privacy Countermeasures	CP. Policies & Practices	Policies & practices	3.2-3.3, 4.1, 5.1; Follow-up questions
	CE. Training & Education	Training & education	3.4-3.5
	CT. Technology	Architectural measures	4.1
		Use case-oriented technological measures	4.2-4.3, 4.5-4.8
		Cryptographic building blocks	4.4, 4.10
		Others technological measures	4.9
Pr. Processes	PrL. System Lifecycle	Security as a part of the system lifecycle	2.2-2.3, 5.2
	PrU. Usage of the System	Use cases of the system as a part of the business processes	4.5-4.8

Figure 7: A reference model of information security and privacy assurance in the intelligent systems and its mapping with the questionnaire in Appendix II [1]

Appendix IV. Supplementary material

- The list of analysed variables and their mapping to the survey questions together with the full list of significant correlation values can be found in supplementary materials in [31].
- The list of significant Spearman's correlation between the variable can be found in supplementary materials in [31].

References

- [1] M. Bakhtina, R. Matulevicius, and L. Malina, “Information security and privacy management in intelligent transportation systems,” *Complex Systems Informatics and Modeling Quarterly (CSIMQ)*, vol. 38, pp. 100–131, 2024. Available: <https://doi.org/10.7250/csimq.2024-38.04>.
- [2] M. Bakhtina, R. Matulevicius, and L. Malina, “Information security and privacy management in intelligent transportation systems,” 2024.
- [3] R. v. Roessing, “The ISACA business model for information security: An integrative and innovative approach,” in *ISSE 2009 securing electronic business processes*, pp. 37–47, Springer, 2010.
- [4] J. McCumber, *Assessing and managing security risk in IT systems: A structured methodology*. Auerbach Publications, 2004.
- [5] Y. Cherdantseva and J. Hilton, “A reference model of information assurance & security,” in *2013 International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security*, pp. 546–555, 2013.
- [6] B. Kitchenham and S. Charters, “Guidelines for performing systematic literature reviews in software engineering,” Tech. Rep. EBSE-2007-01, Jul 2007.
- [7] C. Wohlin, P. Runeson, M. Höst, M. C. Ohlsson, B. Regnell, and A. Wesslén, *Experimentation in software engineering*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [8] M. Khalid, K. Wang, N. Aslam, Y. Cao, N. Ahmad, and M. K. Khan, “From smart parking towards autonomous valet parking: A survey, challenges and future Works,” *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 175, p. 102935, Feb. 2021. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2020.102935>.
- [9] R. Borges and F. Sebé, “An efficient privacy-preserving pay-by-phone system for regulated parking areas,” *International Journal of Information Security*, vol. 20, pp. 715–727, Oct. 2021. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10207-020-00527-2>.
- [10] R. Garra, S. Martínez, and F. Sebé, “A Privacy-Preserving Pay-by-Phone Parking System,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 66, pp. 5697–5706, July 2017. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2016.2634785>.
- [11] L. Zhu, M. Li, Z. Zhang, and Z. Qin, “ASAP: An Anonymous Smart-Parking and Payment Scheme in Vehicular Networks,” *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, vol. 17, pp. 703–715, July 2020. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDSC.2018.2850780>.
- [12] Z. Li, M. Alazab, S. Garg, and M. S. Hossain, “PriParkRec: Privacy-Preserving Decentralized Parking Recommendation Service,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 70, pp. 4037–4050, May 2021. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2021.3074820>.
- [13] M. Weber and I. Podnar Žarko, “A Regulatory View on Smart City Services,” *Sensors*, vol. 19, p. 415, Jan. 2019. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19020415>.
- [14] R. Borges and F. Sebé, “Parking Tickets for Privacy-Preserving Pay-by-Phone Parking,” in *Proceedings of the 18th ACM Workshop on Privacy in the Electronic Society - WPES’19*, (London, United Kingdom), pp. 130–134, ACM Press, 2019. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3338498.3358638>.
- [15] P. Dzurenda, C. A. Tafalla, S. Ricci, and L. Malina, “Privacy-Preserving Online Parking Based on Smart Contracts,” in *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security*, ARES 21, (New York, NY, USA), pp. 1–10, Association for Computing Machinery, Aug. 2021. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3465481.3470058>.
- [16] I. Chatzigiannakis, A. Vitaletti, and A. Pyrgelis, “A privacy-preserving smart parking system using an IoT elliptic curve based security platform,” *Computer Communications*, vol. 89–90, pp. 165–177, Sept. 2016. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comcom.2016.03.014>.

- [17] W. A. Amiri, M. Baza, K. Banawan, M. Mahmoud, W. Alasmary, and K. Akkaya, "Privacy-preserving smart parking system using blockchain and private information retrieval," in *2019 International Conference on Smart Applications, Communications and Networking (SmartNets)*, pp. 1–6, 2019. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/SmartNets48225.2019.9069783>.
- [18] F. Al-Turjman, H. Zahmatkesh, and R. Shahroze, "An overview of security and privacy in smart cities' IoT communications," *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, vol. 33, no. 3, p. e3677, 2022. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ett.3677>.
- [19] P. Dzurenda, F. Jacques, M. Knockaert, M. Laurent, L. Malina, R. Matulevicius, Q. Tang, and A. Tasidou, "Privacy-preserving solution for vehicle parking services complying with EU legislation," *PeerJ Computer Science*, vol. 8, p. e1165, 2022. Available: <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1165>.
- [20] Y. Fang, Y. Zhao, Y. Yu, H. Zhu, X. Du, and M. Guizani, "Blockchain-based privacy-preserving valet parking for self-driving vehicles," *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, vol. 32, no. 4, p. e4239, 2021. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ett.4239>.
- [21] R. Shivers, M. A. Rahman, M. J. H. Faruk, H. Shahriar, A. Cuzzocrea, and V. Clincy, "Ride-hailing for autonomous vehicles: Hyperledger fabric-based secure and decentralize blockchain platform," in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*, pp. 5450–5459, 2021. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/BigData52589.2021.9671379>.
- [22] S. Ramezani, G. Akman, M. T. Damir, and V. Niemi, "Lightweight privacy-preserving ride-sharing protocols for autonomous cars," in *Proceedings of the 6th ACM Computer Science in Cars Symposium, CSCS '22*, (New York, NY, USA), Association for Computing Machinery, 2022. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3568160.3570234>.
- [23] W. Chen, H. Wu, X. Chen, and J. Chen, "A Review of Research on Privacy Protection of Internet of Vehicles Based on Blockchain," *Journal of Sensor and Actuator Networks*, vol. 11, no. 4, 2022. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jsan11040086>.
- [24] Z. Wang, H. Wei, J. Wang, X. Zeng, and Y. Chang, "Security issues and solutions for connected and autonomous vehicles in a sustainable city: A survey," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 14, no. 19, 2022. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912409>.
- [25] W. Chen, H. Wu, X. Chen, and J. Chen, "A review of research on privacy protection of internet of vehicles based on blockchain," *Journal of Sensor and Actuator Networks*, vol. 11, no. 4, 2022. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jsan11040086>.
- [26] N. Sathyanarayana, "A survey on vehicle detection and classification for electronic toll collection applications," in *Distributed Computing and Optimization Techniques: Select Proceedings of ICDCOT 2021*, pp. 101–110, Springer, 2022. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-2281-7_10.
- [27] R. Borges, F. Sebe, and M. Valls, "An anonymous and unlinkable electronic toll collection system," *International Journal of Information Security*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 1151–1162, 2022. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10207-022-00604-8>.
- [28] X. Deng and T. Gao, "Electronic payment schemes based on blockchain in VANETs," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 38296–38303, 2020. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2974964>.
- [29] D. Das, S. Banerjee, and U. Biswas, "Design of a secure blockchain-based toll-tax collection system," in *Micro-Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering: Proceedings of 5th ICMETE 2021*, pp. 183–191, Springer, 2022. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-8721-1_18.
- [30] S. Sutar, S. Chopade, A. Ekadari, and L. Ahire, "Security based electronic toll collection using nfc and android application,"

- [31] M. Bakhtina, R. Matulevicius, and L. Malina, “Supplementary material for empirical study of information security and privacy management in intelligent transportation systems in Estonia and South Moravia,” Apr. 2024. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10960351>.
- [32] H. Sharp, A. Finkelstein, and G. Galal, “Stakeholder identification in the requirements engineering process,” in *Proceedings. Tenth International Workshop on Database and Expert Systems Applications. DEXA 99*, pp. 387–391, 1999. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/DEXA.1999.795198>.
- [33] S. Boslaugh, *Statistics in a Nutshell, 2nd Edition*. O’Reilly Media, Incorporated, 2012.